

SYNTHESIS OF 6-HYDROXY-3-ALKYL (ARYL)CHROMONES

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2-Acylhydroquinones on condensation with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium gave 6-hydroxy-3-alkyl(aryl)chromones. The hydroquinones, chromones, as well as their functional derivatives have been described.

A review of the existing literature shows that our knowledge of 6-hydroxychromones, coumarins and flavones is very scanty, while 6-hydroxy-3-alkyl (aryl) chromones are not at all known. The present paper describes the preparation of such compounds.

Mahal, Rai and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1120) have shown that the *o*-hydroxyphenylbenzyl ketones condense with ethyl formate and give isoflavones, which otherwise were inaccessible or could not be synthesised directly. Using this method acylhydroquinones were condensed with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium to give 6-hydroxy-3-alkylchromones.

Kuroda and Wada (*Sci. Papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, 1938, 34, 1740) prepared 2-butyrylhydroquinone by Fries' migration of 4-methoxyphenyl butyrate (m.p. 175°). The same ketone has been prepared in this work by (a) the condensation of hydroquinone with butyryl chloride, (b) Fries' migration of hydroquinone dibutyrate, and (c) demethylation of 2-butyrylhydroquinone dimethyl ether.

2-Butyrylhydroquinone, prepared by any one of these methods, however, melted at 101°. Evidently the melting point reported by the above authors appears to be incorrect

Likewise, Finzi (*Monats*, 1905, 26, 1135) obtained 2-phenylacetylhydroquinone by the condensation of hydroquinone with phenylacetyl chloride and reported the melting point of the substance as 170°, while in the present work it melts at 113°.

On account of this uncertainty, the acylhydroquinones required in this work were prepared in almost all cases by at least two independent methods and their identity was confirmed by preparing their functional derivatives. The overall yields of the acylhydroquinones, prepared by any of the above methods, were only 5 to 7%.

In order to see the accessibility of the reaction of Mahal, Rai and Venkataraman (*loc. cit.*) this reaction was tried on 2-acetylhydroquinone when 6-hydroxychromone, identical with that obtained by David and Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1902, 38, 2547) was isolated in good yields. The reactions involved are given above.

By following exactly the same procedure chromones, tabulated in the Table II, have been prepared and their identity confirmed by their functional derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dimethyl Ether of 2-Butyrylhydroquinone.—Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.2 M) was added in small lots to a mixture of hydroquinone dimethyl ether (0.2 M), butyryl chloride (0.2 M), dissolved in dry and freshly distilled nitrobenzene (80 c.c.). On keeping overnight, the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours and then decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid. The solvent was removed by steam-distillation and the remaining mass was extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water, twice with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and again with water. It was then dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the ether removed. The 2-butyrylhydroquinone dimethyl ether, thus obtained, was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 172°-175°/25 mm., yield 70%. (Found: C, 69.2; H 7.8. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the usual method, was crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 153-54°. (Found: N, 15.7. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15.85 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 174-75°. (Found: N, 14.5. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 14.53 per cent).

The other ethers, prepared in a similar manner from hydroquinone dimethyl ether and the requisite acyl chloride, have been described in Table I.

Preparation of 2-Butyrylhydroquinone. Condensation of Hydroquinone with Butyryl Chloride (Method I).—Hydroquinone (0.1 M) and butyryl chloride (0.1 M) were dissolved in dry distilled nitrobenzene (40 c.c.) and freshly powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1 M) was gradually added to it with ice cooling. On keeping overnight, it was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours, when the colour of the mixture became red. It was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The solvent was removed and the residue extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the ether removed. On keeping overnight it solidified. It was then crystallised from benzene (charcoal), m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 6.7. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.66 per cent).

Dibenzoyl derivative, prepared by the usual method, crystallised from methyl alcohol in white needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 74.25; H, 5.3. $C_{26}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.2; H, 5.2 per cent).

Fries Migration of Hydroquinone Dibutyrate (Method II).—Hydroquinone dibutyrate was prepared by adding butyryl chloride (0.2 M) to hydroquinone (0.1 M) in small lots with vigorous shaking. When the addition was complete, it was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours and then poured in ice water. The liquid obtained was taken in ether and washed with sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and then with water. The ether extract was dried over magnesium sulphate (anhydrous), and the ether removed. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure. It solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (60°-80°) in colorless plates, m.p. 41-42°. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 7.2. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.05; H, 7.2 per cent).

Hydroquinone dibutyrate (0.1 M) was thoroughly mixed with finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1 M) and the mixture was heated at 150°-160° for 5 hours with stirring. On cooling it was decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid when a black liquid separated. This was taken up in ether, washed first with water and then with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline washings were acidified and again extracted with ether. The latter extract on removal of the solvent gave 2-butyrylhydroquinone, which crystallised from benzene (charcoal), m.p. 101°.

Demethylation of Dimethyl Ether of 2-Butyrylhydroquinone (Method III).—Dimethyl ether of 2-butyrylhydroquinone (0.04 M) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of hydrobromic acid in acetic acid (0°). The mixture was heated on a sand-bath for 6 hours under reflux. The whole product was poured on ice when a viscous mass separated. Under these circumstances it was dissolved in ether, and washed with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline washings were acidified, extracted with ether, washed free of acids, and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the ether, the residue solidified. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 101°.

All these products obtained by these three different methods have been shown to be identical by finding their mixed melting points.

Preparation of 6-Hydroxy-3-ethylchromone.—2-Butyrylhydroquinone (5 g.) was added to dry and freshly distilled ethyl formate (150 c.c.) and the mixture was added to powdered sodium (10 g.) during 2 hours, with ice cooling. After 20 hours the reaction mixture became dull red. It was then decomposed by ice water and it was extracted with ether to remove the unchanged substances. After acidification of the alkaline water extract, and keeping it for about 4 hours, fine needles of 6-hydroxy-3-ethylchromone was obtained. It was filtered and crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 181°. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 5.1. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.3; H, 5.26 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-ethylchromone was prepared by dissolving the above chromone (1 g.) in dry acetone (20 c.c.) and adding to it anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) and methyl iodide (5 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. The solid obtained after removal of the solvent was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and then with

water. It crystallised from petroleum ether (60°-80°), m.p. 66°. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 5.9. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.24; H, 5.9 per cent).

6-Acetoxy-3-ethylchromone was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 6-hydroxy-3-ethylchromone (1 g.), acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g.) for 3 hours and pouring it in ice water. The product was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 90°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.3; H, 5.2 per cent).

The other 2-acylhydroquinones, chromones, as well as their functional derivatives have been prepared in a similar manner and are described in Table II.

TABLE I

Compounds. [H=hydroquinone]	Mol. formula.	M.p.	B.p.	Found		Calc.		Solvent used and remarks.
				C.	H.	C.	H.	
Dimethyl ether of 2-n-caproyl-H	$C_{14}H_{20}O_3$	—	175-80°/15mm.	71.3%	8.5%	71.2%	8.5%	Colorless liquid.
Dimethyl ether of 2-heptyl-H	$C_{15}H_{22}O_3$	34-35°	175-80°/5	71.1	8.9	72.0	8.8	MeOH
Dimethyl ether of 2-lauroyl-H	—	—	180-85°/1.2	—	—	—	—	B.p. 175-78°/0.2-0.3 mm. (cf. Heilbron <i>et al.</i> , <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> 1942, 660).
Dimethyl ether of phenylacetyl-H	—	49°	—	—	—	—	—	Petroleum ether (60°-80°), m.p. 49° (cf. Kauffmann and Grombach, <i>Annalen</i> , 1906, 88, 344).
Dimethyl ether of 2-phenylpropionyl-H	$C_{17}H_{18}O_3$	—	210-12°/2-3	75.6	6.8	75.5	6.6	—

TABLE II

Compounds. [C=chromone; H=hydroquinone]	Prepared from.	Mol. formula.	M.p.	B.p.	Found.		Calc.	Solvent used and remarks.
					C.	H.		
6-Hydroxy-C	2-Acetyl-H & ethyl formate	—	241-42°	—	—	—	—	M.p. 243° (cf. David and Kostanecki, <i>Ber.</i> , 1902, 88, 2547).
6-Acetoxy-C	6-Hydroxy-C	—	126-27°	—	—	—	—	M.p. 127° (cf. David and Kostanecki, <i>loc. cit.</i>)
6-Methoxy-C	„	$C_{10}H_8O_3$	97-98°	—	C, 68.3%	H, 4.6	68.2% 4.54	Petroleum ether (60°-80°)
2-n-Valeryl-H	H & n-valeryl chloride by method I.	$C_{11}H_{14}O_3$	—	180-85°/15 mm.	C, 68.15	H, 7.2	68.05 7.2	—
6-Hydroxy-3-n-propyl-C	n-Valeryl-H & ethyl formate	$C_{12}H_{16}O_3$	119°	—	C, 70.5	H, 5.8	70.6 5.9	Dilute MeOH

TABLE II (contd.)

Compounds.	Prepared from.	Mol. formula.	M.p.	B.p.	Found.	Calc.	Solvent used & remarks.
6-Methoxy-3- <i>n</i> -propyl-C	6-Hydroxy-3- <i>n</i> -propyl-C	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	48-49°	—	C, 71.6% H, 6.5	71.55% 6.4	Petroleum ether
2- <i>iso</i> Valeryl-H	Hydroquinone & <i>iso</i> valeryl chloride by method I	—	114-15°	—	—	—	CCl ₄ (cf. Klinger & Standke, <i>Ber.</i> , 1891, 24, 1345).
6-Hydroxy-3- <i>isopropyl</i> -C	2- <i>iso</i> Propyl-H & ethyl formate	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₃	191-92°	—	C, 70.5 H, 5.8	70.6 5.9	Dil. EtOH, yield very poor.
6-Acetoxy-3- <i>isopropyl</i> -C	Acetylation of 6-hydroxy-3- <i>iso</i> -propyl-C	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄	88°	—	C, 68.3 H, 5.7	68.3 5.67	Dil. EtOH
2- <i>n</i> -Caproyl-H	(1) Hydroquinone & <i>n</i> -caproyl chloride by method I	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₃	81-82°	—	C, 69.3 H, 7.72	69.23 7.7	Benzene.
	(2) Demethylation of dimethyl ether of 2-caproyl-H by method III		81-82° (mixed)				
6-Hydroxy- <i>n</i> -butyl-C	Hydroquinone & ethyl formate	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	138°	—	C, 71.5 H, 6.6	71.55 6.4	Dil. EtOH
6-Methoxy-3- <i>n</i> -butyl-C	Methylation of 6-hydroxy-3- <i>n</i> -butyl-C	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃	63°	—	C, 72.4 H, 6.9	72.4 6.9	Petroleum ether (60-80°)
H-diheptoate	H & heptoyl chloride heated on a water-bath for 6 hours	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₄	57-48°	—	C, 71.9 H, 9.1	71.8 8.9	MeOH
2-Heptoyl-H	(1) H & heptoyl chloride by method I	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃	118°	—	C, 70.2 H, 8.0	70.26 8.1	Benzene.
	(2) Fries' migration of diheptoate by method II		118° (mixed)				
	(3) Demethylation of dimethyl ether of 2-heptoyl-H by method III		118° (mixed)				
6-Hydroxy-3- <i>n</i> -pentyl-C	2-Heptyol-H & ethyl formate	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃	146°	—	C, 72.3 H, 6.8	72.4 6.9	Dil. MeOH
6-Acetoxy-3- <i>n</i> -pentyl-C	Acetylation of 6-hydroxy-3- <i>n</i> -pentyl-C	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄	90-91°	—	C, 70.1 H, 6.7	70.0 6.6	Do
2-Lauroyl-H	Demethylation of its dimethyl ether (cf. Table I) by method III	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₃	101°	—	C, 73.8 H, 9.5	74.0 9.6	Petroleum ether (60°-80°)
6-Hydroxy 3- <i>n</i> -decyl-H	2-Lauroyl-H & ethyl formate	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₃	115°	—	C, 75.3 H, 8.7	75.5 8.6	Dil. EtOH

TABLE II (contd.)

Compounds.	Prepared from.	Mol. formula.	M.p.	B.p.	Found.	Calc.	Solvent used and remarks.
2-Phenylacetyl-H	(1) H & phenylacetyl chloride by method I	$C_{14}H_{12}O_3$	113°	—	C, 73.5% H, 5.3	73.7% 5.26	CCl_4
	(2) Demethylation of dimethyl ether of 2-phenylacetyl-H by method III		113° (mixed)				
Diacetyl derivative of 2-phenylacetyl-H	Acetylation of 2-phenylacetyl-H	$C_{18}H_{16}O_5$	141-142°	—	C, 69.1 H, 5.3	69.2 5.1	MeOH
6-Hydroxy-3-n-pentyl-C (6-hydroxy isoflavone)	2-Phenylacetyl-H & ethyl formate	$C_{15}H_{10}O_3$	215-16°	—	C, 75.45 H, 4.1	75.6 4.2	Dil. MeOH
6-Methoxyisoflavone	Methylation of 6-hydroxyisoflavone	$C_{16}H_{12}O_3$	170-71°	—	C, 76.1 H, 4.4	76.2 4.6	Do
6-Acetoxyisoflavone	Acetylation of 6-hydroxy isoflavone	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	152°	—	C, 72.9 H, 4.4	72.82 4.2	Dil. MeOH
2-β-Phenylpropionyl-H	(1) Hydroquinone & hydrocinnamoyl chloride by method I	$C_{15}H_{14}O_3$	119°	—	C, 74.3 H, 5.9	74.38 5.8	Do
	(2) Demethylation of dimethyl ether of 2-phenylpropionyl-H		119° (mixed)				
Dibenzoyl derivative of 2-β-phenylpropionyl-H	Benzoylation of 2-phenylpropionyl-H	$C_{23}H_{22}O_5$	157°	—	C, 77.5 H, 4.9	77.3 4.9	"
6-Hydroxy-3-benzyl-C	2-Phenylpropionyl-H & ethyl formate	$C_{16}H_{12}O_3$	226°	—	C, 76.3 H, 4.8	76.2 4.7	"
6-Methoxy-3-benzyl-C	Methylation of 6-hydroxy-3-benzyl-C.	$C_{17}H_{14}O_3$	98-99°	—	C, 76.8 H, 5.3	76.7 5.26	Dilute ethyl alcohol
6-Acetoxy-3-benzyl-C	Acetylation of 6-hydroxy-3-benzyl-C	$C_{18}H_{14}O_4$	128°	—	C, 73.5 H, 4.8	73.48 4.75	"